

The Stylistic features of set expressions in English language

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Abstract

The main purpose of this article is to consider the study of Phraseological word combinations, stable word groups, and the use of stylistic way. In addition, to organise the information about English proverbs, and types of stylistic device is English cliché.

Keywords: Phraseology, phraseological word combinations, English proverbs, cliché.

Introduction

The idea that phraseology has the right to exist as a separate linguistic discipline was first put forward by Kunin. He also introduced the term phraseological stylistics to denote the study of stylistic properties of Phraseological Units. Kunin viewed phraseological stylistics as part of both general stylistics and phraseology. He developed his ideas of stylistic use of Phraseological Units in his subsequent works. In Russia, stylistic studies of phraseology have flourished after Kunin (1964), for example, Boldireva 1967, Sviridova 1968, Shadrin 1969, Naciscione 1976, Danchenko 1977, Zhantlesova 1978, Melerovich 1982, Moshiasvili 1982, Dubinsky 1985. This trend also continues today for example, Ryzhkina 2003.

In Western Europe, scholarly interest in phraseology and in stylistic use of Phraseological Units in particular developed much later, Cowie. Following Kunin, Gläser voices a plea for phraseo-stylistics as a subject of stylistic description in its own right to study the communicative effects of phraseological units and their occasional, individual modifications. Further studies are also devoted to the stylistic potential of phraseological units in text. Research on stylistic changes of phraseological units in text has recently been on the increase; for instance, Sabban offers a thorough analysis of occasional variations of French and German phraseology in use, and explores the text-building potential of Phraseological Units in discourse. Various types and genres of texts have attracted much attention, including media texts and advertisements.

In paremiology the term anti-proverb was introduced by Mieder, it has been accepted by proverb scholars as a general term to denote innovative changes in traditional proverbs, for example, Mieder 1989; Mieder and Litovkina 1999; Walter and Mokienko 2005; Barta 2006; Litovkina and Mieder 2006. This approach works very well if the first part of the proverb has been fully or partly preserved in stylistic use, as in cases of extended metaphor, pun, replacement, zeugma, and others, while believe it is not applicable in cases of phraseological allusion and in cases of phraseological saturation when a number of stylistic changes are instantiated in one context in a stretch of discourse.

Whether phraseological stylistics should be singled out as a separate area is another issue. However, a need clearly exists to examine Phraseological Units in use and the rules and processes determining stylistic changes, many of which exceed the boundaries of one sentence. Cognitive stylistics is an appropriate discipline for these purposes as a cognitive approach to language use focuses on meaning and its development. Two essential avenues of exploration and observation are the relationship between phraseological meaning and thought in stylistic instantiations, and changes and developments in discourse, including visual discourse. One of the objectives of stylistics is to study and understand the general principles and procedures upon which stylistic changes are built and to account for the cognitive mechanisms underlying the functioning of Phraseological Units in discourse. The growing interest in phraseology can be explained partly by the complicated processes which occur in this part of vocabulary, partly by a focus on lexicography as well as an increasing interest in discourse in general and its relevance to pedagogy. Our conception of discursal use is bound to influence our way of teaching. Exploration of Phraseological Units in discourse is crucial not only in the theoretical sphere but also in applied aspects.

A cognitive approach to stylistic analysis of Phraseological Units in discourse is a transdisciplinary search. It calls for new ways of thinking about phraseology and stylistics, and their close links with fringe disciplines, such as psycholinguistics and cognitive linguistics, acknowledging the role of psychology in discourse comprehension, learning, and teaching, especially for complex language units like Phraseological Units.

Style is fundamental for analysis of Phraseological Units in discourse. Indeed, style is

part of the meaning of Phraseological Units. It is one of the elements of the semantic structure of phraseological meaning . The cognitive dimension is particularly important in understanding the process of creating phraseological meaning in text. Cognitive psychology is the study of perceptual processes, especially the processing of a flow of words, as well as recognition, creativity, and imagery. Creativity in use of phraseology implies a capacity for random and non-traditional thinking, seeking to produce novel forms of Phraseological Units in discourse and introduce new features in their image. This approach calls for a greater awareness of changes in discourse and a readiness to accept new stylistic formations as facts of discourse. [1, p 20]

A proverb is a brief, simple, and popular saying, or a phrase that gives advice and effectively embodies a commonplace truth based on practical experience or common sense. A proverb may have an allegorical message behind its odd appearance. The reason of popularity is due to its usage in spoken language, as well as in folk literature.

“A proverb is a traditional saying which offers advice or presents a moral in a short and pithy manner. Paradoxically, many phrases which are called ‘proverbial’ are not proverbs as we now understand the term. We might for instance refer to ‘the proverbial fly on the wall’ or say that something is ‘as dead as the proverbial dodo’, although neither of these phrases alludes to a proverb. The confusion dates from before the eighteenth century, when the term ‘proverb’ also covered metaphorical phrases, similes, and descriptive epithets, and was used far more loosely than it is today. Nowadays we would normally expect a proverb to be cast in the form of a sentence”. [2, p 14]

Proverbs exist in every language, and often deal with similar topics. One of these common topics is knowledge, for only by learning can one truly be successful in any task.

- **“A little bit of knowledge is a dangerous thing”**

If you say this proverb to someone, it means that you believe someone knows just enough to potentially be dangerous, but not enough that the danger they post is acceptable. This often can be said of cases where acting with only incomplete information is likely to create chaos or danger. For example, if a business executive sees that another company is advertising their products to children, and he wants his own company to do the same thing, he may be on the

verge of doing a very dangerous thing. If advertising to children requires special permission from the trade regulation committee of the government, but his company does not have this, he may get into big trouble by trying this new idea. Similarly, if a doctor still in training saw an experienced doctor treat a patient one way, and tries to replicate it, he may do much more harm than good if it turns out to be a different situation. This proverb is used to show other people that they do not have the full picture of something, and need to first see the forest – instead of individual trees (to understand the larger picture instead of being confined to the details) – before taking action or making a permanent decision.

- *The worst part about being an acupuncturist is that some people take a weekend and get a “certificate” that allows them to put needles in people. In their case, however, **a little bit of knowledge is a dangerous thing** and they often do not have the skills to actually heal people.*
- *I can't believe the medical intern tried to write a prescription! He definitely did not know enough to get the right medications and dosages. **A little bit of knowledge is a dangerous thing.***
- *“**A journey of a thousand miles begins with a single step!**”*

This proverb means that anything that seems like a very long process – the journey of a thousand miles, for example – must be taken one step at a time. While the whole project may seem daunting, and like it may take a lot of effort, it actually only takes one step at a time to get started. This proverb is often said to encourage someone to take action on something that they think is overwhelming.

- *The point of the speech that the PhD graduates gave to their younger peers was that their **journey of a thousand miles began with a single step**, and to break down the large steps into smaller steps that they could take one at a time.*
- *Writing a novel is a long journey, **but all journeys of a thousand miles begin with a single step.***
- *“**Give a man a fish, he eats for a day. Teach a man to fish, he eats for a lifetime**”*

This proverb actually exists in many different languages, though it might be in a slightly different form. Either way, the meaning of this proverb is that, if you really want to help

someone, you should not just do it by completing the things for them. This creates a feeling of dependence, and it very easy for the other person to never think about what they need to do in order to be successful themselves. Instead, the best way to help someone is to teach them how to do something. If you teach a man how to fish, he will be able to use that skill over and over again to feed himself, whether or not you are standing there by his side to help him. This is a great proverb if you are reminding parents about helping their children learn. Even though every parent wants their child to be the best, you must allow them to struggle and learn how to overcome the types of challenges that they face, so that one day they can meet these challenges without having to have someone guide them through it.

- *Many of the best nonprofit organizations that build schools, provide health care, teach locals, and other things operate with the mindset that the people they are providing resources to will one day be able to sustain their ways of living by themselves. **Give a man a fish, he eats for a day. Teach a man to fish, he eats for a lifetime**, so education and learning how to do something is far more important than giving people a bunch of resources that they will no longer have once you leave*
- *It took Little George’s parents a long time to realize this, but their coddling their son was not helping him at all. He ended up not knowing how to dress himself even though he was already starting school, and he still drank infant formula because he liked it. However, **give a man a fish, he eats for a day. Teach a man to fish, he eats for a lifetime**. Once he started school, they stopped helping him so directly.*
- **“Great minds think alike”**

If you tell someone that great minds think alike, you are most likely referring to the fact that you and they thought of the same thing at the same time. If you are brainstorming for something, and it just so happens that both of you come up with the same idea for something, one of you can exclaim, “Great minds think alike!” to signify that you were just thinking the same thing. Whether or not either of you is actually a “great mind” does not matter that much. As long as you are able to say that you two were thinking along the same lines, you can lightheartedly say that great minds think alike.

- *You think putting everything in a massive to do list sounds like a great idea, too? It looks like **great minds think alike!***
- *Our project manager asked us to write down all the potential problems that this idea could have that we could think of, and it turns out that three of my ideas were the same as yours! **Great minds must think alike!***

[3, p 4]

“The cliché applies also to almost any situation, subject, characterization, figure of speech, or object – in short, any sign – that has become overly familiar or commonplace. Because the novelty or frequency of an expression's use varies across different times and places, whether or not it is a cliché depends largely on who uses it, the context in which it is used, and who is making the judgment. E.g. times are changing, as easy as a piece of cake, as wet as blood, as clear as day”.[4, p 6]

Clichés are overused expressions that have been said so many times, by so many people, that they've rather lost their meaning and don't always say very much. Peoples use phrases like this so often that they don't even realise it; some like to spout clichéd advice such as “every cloud has a silver lining” because they aren't sure what else to say. Clichés are often idioms – that is, a figurative phrase that has an implied meaning rather than a literal one. George Orwell said of such expressions: “Never use a metaphor, simile, or other figure of speech which you are used to seeing in print.” In other words, don't rehash the same phrases everyone else does – it usually doesn't add anything to what you're saying!

- **“At the end of the day”**

This is a cliché you are likely to hear a lot if you come to the UK. It means “when everything has been considered”, and it's usually used to precede what one considers to be the crux of the matter. An example of its use might be as follows:

*“We talked about the situation and I advised him what I thought he should do, but **at the end of the day**, it's his decision.”*

A less clichéd – and more economical – way of phrasing this might be to replace “at the end of the day” with “ultimately”, or just to get rid of it altogether; as with many modern clichés, you'll often find that the sentence works just as well without it.[5, p 2]

A cliché expression is a fixed, conventionalized multi-word expression which has become overused to the point of losing its original meaning or effect.

Cliché:

fixed: the expression in the form that is recognized cannot be changed, or only to a limited degree by filling in specified open slots.

conventionalized: the phrase is recognized by many speakers as a unit, instead of being put together word for word.

overused: this aspect is crucial but subjective and therefore harder to pin down. Many other multi-word expressions are accepted as a normal part of the lexicon, while cliché expressions are marked as ´ formulaic, tired, unoriginal. [6, p 35]

The first type of set expressions is the cliché. A cliché is generally defined as an expression that has become hackneyed, trite. It has lost its precise meaning by constant reiteration; in other words it has become stereotyped. It has lost its freshness, the aesthetic generating power it once had. There is always a contradiction between what is aimed at and what is actually attained. Most of the widely recognized word combinations which have been adopted by the language are unjustly classified as clichés. [7,p 132].

Conclusion

In Conclusion, Phraseology is the study of phraseological stable word groups and types of classifications, using form in the context. Phraseological word combinations based on phraseological units, stable word groups, idiomaticity in linguistics. Also, it belongs to stylistics especially ready-made word groups characterised by linguo-stylistic form. English proverbs are traditionally defined with the term ready-made words and not created during the communication. English cliché applies also to almost any situation, subject, characterization, figure of speech, or object – in short, any sign – that has become overly familiar or commonplace

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